

Work Of Judicial Whistleblowers (Comparative Analysis Study)

Marwa Abduljaleel Shunabah

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 06, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: June 19, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Judicial , Defense , The Validity Of Litigation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6667879</p>	<p><i>Judicial notification is the essential procedure defined by the Iraqi Civil Procedures Law in force, to enable the litigants of the case to be aware of the judicial procedures taken against each of them, in the implementation of the principle of confrontation between the litigants, which entails activating a basic guarantee in the judiciary, which is the principle of ensuring the validity of litigation. However, the validity of litigation alone is not sufficient to reflect a fair and efficient judiciary in the consideration of the cases that are brought before it without there being a waste of time or expenses; Therefore, the purpose is to reduce the effort on the person charge of reporting or reduce cases of postponement of the case and link it with time, as well as reduce cases of invalidity. There should be a legal regulation for the use of electronic means in the judicial notification within the framework of the Civil Procedures Law in addition to the traditional reporting method. Because the problem of slowness in achieving justice is the real challenge to the rules of litigation in the pleadings law, which aims to achieve the resolution of cases in the shortest time, least effort, and minimum expenses without wasting or violating the guarantees of litigation and respecting the rights of the defense</i></p>

Introduction

Thanks to God, who, by his grace, are the good deeds, and prayers and peace be upon our Master Muhammad, who sent us mercy in life and after death, and on his family and companions and peace, but after:-

Time is an element within the framework of the civil judiciary, particularly about judicial reports, and the time factor is also important, which in turn reflects the resolution of litigation in favor of one party without another, which also has a stimulating role in creating what facilitates the work of judicial whistleblowers to resolve cases without delay, i.e. time in the judicial field is of paramount importance because it is linked to justice, which is required by the necessity of life itself, and therefore the requirements of studying the subject of the role of online reporting in facilitating the work of judicial whistleblowers, we have to deal with the following paragraphs: **The importance of the study**

The problem of slow justice is the real challenge to the litigation rules of the Litigation Act, which aim to achieve the resolution of cases in the shortest time, with the least effort and the lowest expenses without wasting or exceeding the guarantees of litigation and respect for the rights of the defense.

This slowness may be manifested by traditional reporting methods by judicial whistleblowers, so confronting delays in the process of judicial reporting and resulting in delays in the resolution of judicial proceedings requires the legislator to take part in the legislative amendments by organizing legal provisions under the Iraqi civil arguments law in force, regulating the possibility of the court conducting judicial reports electronically, to simplify or reduce the number of reporting procedures.

It is, therefore, necessary to appoint a specialized staff for electronic reporting work in each court or justice department, as well as the events of formations in all departments of the state to follow up on the completion of such reports, the continuation of the reporting courses to qualify whistleblowers for reporting work, these entities are under the supervision of the Directorate of Judicial Reporting in the center of each province headed by a director and several whistleblowers with the duty of traditional and electronic reporting

Statements of the problem

The problem of research is reflected in the frequent postponement of civil proceedings due to the frequent delay in reporting by judicial whistleblowers, as doctrinal studies reflecting the repercussions of reality have shown that there are several problems in the adoption of traditional judicial reporting alone, including about delays in reporting procedures by the police, including due to the distance between the court and the residence of the person to be informed, especially in villages and rural areas, because of the lack of mail or due to the difficulty of the road, or the lack of rapid transportation, or lack of cooperation. Between the court and other circles, this is on the part of the.

On the other hand, the problem is the lack of legal presence of electronic reporting, although important in facilitating the work of judicial whistleblowers and speeding up the resolution of civil proceedings, the law has

defined a certain form of judicial reporting resulting in its invalidity, and if the law requires judicial reporting in a particular case, it is the only means of such knowledge, i.e. when it is not done or complained, it may be replaced or supplemented by another means.

1. Reducing the effort in the work of judicial whistleblowers and speeding up the completion of the tasks assigned to them and thereby reducing the cases of postponement of the case as well as reducing the cases of nullity, so as long as the purpose of the electronic reporting is achieved.

2. Reducing the costs required by traditional reporting, as the opponent must be notified of the appearance in court on the appointed day of the case and also informed of the petition and each note submitted by one of the litigants and also informed of the ruling and when appealing the appeal and when appealing the distinction also must be communicated to the distinguished person in a form of petition to other judicial reports which hinders the resolution of the case, and the notifications may take several months and sometimes a year or more and the opponent evades reporting, although the law The arguments must take into account the place of work or residence of the person to be notified when issuing the reporting paper, but not less than the period between the person to be notified and the day appointed to plead for three days, except for urgent matters, i.e. the court must take into account the status of the addressee in terms of the complexities of the case, the time of preparation of his defence, the available means of transportation, the climate and its impact on transportation.

3. Simplifying the formality of judicial work; reporting by modern means of communication is no different from reporting in traditional ways;

In our study, we will adopt the role of electronic reporting in facilitating the work of whistleblowers within the framework of Iraqi legislation within the scope of the civil arguments law in force, and the electronic signature law as well as the internal system of the Federal Supreme Court, yet we will provide some aspect of the comparative laws as quoted as required by the subject matter, and we will strengthen legislative positions with the practical and practical approach to comparative justice whenever necessary, to show the extent to which these judicial provisions conform to these positions

First research

The effectiveness of online reporting in facilitating the work of whistleblowers

Judicial communications seek to achieve a fair justice away from all doubts by inviting parties to attend at the designated time and place to hear the case, and because electronic reporting has a role in the speed of adjudication of the existing case as well as the low costs and ease of use; Because of the invalidity of reporting and its return⁽¹⁾ this is what we will try to study by clarifying the concept of electronic reporting in the first requirement of this research, and in the second requirement of it we will determine the vital scope of electronic reporting.

The first requirement

The concept of online reporting

Researching the concept of electronic reporting as a means that can be used by judicial reporting specialists leads us to introduce it and then indicate the legal basis for it, and this is what we will look at in the following two sections:

Section one

Introducing online reporting

Judicial reporting is the basis established by the Iraqi Civil Arguments Act, which is in force, to enable the litigants to be informed of a particular judicial procedure by handing over a copy of a particular paper⁽²⁾. Judicial communication is not far from being a means of informing the other party of the actions taken in the face of it by the principle of confrontation between adversaries⁽³⁾, which entails activating a guarantee of a basis in the judiciary, namely the principle of ensuring the validity of litigation⁽⁴⁾.

However, our Iraqi legislator did not know the judicial reporting, but under article (13/1) of the civil arguments law in force, persons in charge of judicial reporting, represented by persons appointed by the Minister of Justice, postal officials, and police officers in remote areas, were identified⁽⁵⁾.

However, part of the jurisprudence defined it as a formal judicial procedure intended to supplement the knowledge of the person to be informed of the content of the order to be communicated to him⁽⁶⁾, and another aspect,⁽⁷⁾as informing the person to be informed of the judicial papers and the actions taken against him in the manner established by law.

Another aspect he defined as the official means of informing the parties of a particular procedure of judicial papers in general and enabling them to access it and hand over a copy of it⁽⁸⁾, while another aspect defined it as the main official means of informing the parties of a particular procedure of the judicial papers in general⁽⁹⁾, and was also defined as the receipt of judicial papers to natural and moral persons to be informed of the content of

the reporting paper or to appear on the day and hour specified in the court reporting paper. The stakeholder to consider a particular matter for the court⁽¹⁰⁾.

He notes that the content of these definitions was focused on the fact that judicial reporting is a means by which the person is informed of the actions taken against him, as no action may be taken against a person without being able to know about it and without allowing him to defend himself⁽¹¹⁾, and we support the position of our Iraqi legislator in not defining judicial reporting; who are on the task of judicial reporting to break the doubt about their identification⁽¹²⁾.

About online reporting, it is no different from the traditional judicial reporting work, as a judicial procedure is intended to inform the person to be informed of the judicial papers but is distinct from the traditional reporting in the use of electronic means designed to this end.

Despite the lack of legal presence of electronic reporting under the Civil Arguments Act, an aspect has defined it as a procedural act by declaring the opponent in the case of any judicial action to be encountered through the use of modern means of communication without the need for physical transmission and the search for the citizen of the declared person so that it can replace the traditional methods of modern advertising⁽¹³⁾.

online reporting is a modern concept in line with the technological developments that have entered the modern world and to take advantage of this technology within the framework of judicial work and facilitate its role in adjudicating the case by overcoming the difficulties that the judicial reporting officer may face when reporting expenses and time as well as mistakes in following traditional judicial reporting procedures.

In other words, electronic reporting depends on the use of new and modern means of reporting that have an auxiliary and effective role for traditional reporting methods to reduce the scope of disputes regarding the validity of reporting, electronic reporting is an effective means of communicating with the dilapidated opponents in the case and informing them of the latest procedures and lawsuits⁽¹⁴⁾.

Therefore, we can note that the characteristics of electronic judicial reporting are the characteristics of traditional reporting, which are determined by:

First. Reporting is an official means of being issued by a competent public servant and an argument against all people that can only be challenged by forgery.

Secondly. Prepare a judicial paper informing the opponent of a particular incident to be aware of it.

Thirdly, a procedural action issued by the court to inform the opponent by those who have specified the law for that task;

Section two

Legal basis for online reporting

We mean the legal basis for electronic reporting, which is accepted by legal logic and justice to justify the procedure of electronic reporting, despite the absence of legal regulation of electronic reporting in the Iraqi civil arguments law in force, some reasons justify the importance of its role in facilitating the work of the specialist in judicial reporting, namely:

First. Formality must be simplified to ensure the public interest :-

Simplifying formality is one of the objectives that our Iraqi legislators aim to achieve without compromising the origin of the right, because procedural formalities are not a cause of the waste of rights, ensuring that the litigants obtain their rights most easily. The justice of the judicial rulings is not alone in ensuring those rights, but must be obtained without wasting time or expenses⁽¹⁵⁾.

Secondly. The role of the positive judge and the spirit of the legal text: -

The application of the law as required by justice is not based on the literal application of the law, and the judge may therefore interpret the text in such a way that it can absorb and contain all future events within its scope.

When drafting the legal text, the legislator formulates it on the assumption that the text will keep pace with what is happening in the future, so interpreting the legal text to make its application appropriate to everything that occurs in the future means strengthening the positive role of the judge and not putting antagonism as an arena controlled by the litigants, but the judge may intervene to achieve the right and ensure justice⁽¹⁶⁾. and based on the spirit of the text containing the legislator's will to have a living legal text in line with new developments and changes⁽¹⁷⁾.

Accordingly, it is conceivable that the texts relating to judicial reporting should be based on the civil procedure law, and therefore can be interpreted in such a way as to allow the specialist to report the use of an electronic means to achieve the purpose of judicial reporting, which is to achieve the knowledge to be communicated with the judicial proceedings taken in the face of it⁽¹⁸⁾, but the said law has identified a certain form of judicial reporting resulting in its invalidity. The only one for this flag⁽¹⁹⁾, therefore, may not be replaced by anything other than what it has set for its conduct

Thirdly. Laws and regulations related to electronic means: -

We mean here that reporting one of the electronic means is not a strange thing under Iraqi legislation, and this is what we note in:

A. The Law on Electronic Signature and Electronic Transactions of Iraq No. (87) of 2012, although this law included the legislative framework for the use of electronic means in the conduct and integrity of electronic transactions, the legislator excluded court proceedings, judicial declarations, declaration of attendance and judicial orders from its scope⁽²⁰⁾.

In. The rules of procedure of the Federal Court, article (21) of the Rules of Procedure for The Conduct of The Supreme Federal Court No. (1) of 2005, stipulate that ((the Federal Supreme Court may make notifications in its area of jurisdiction by means of e-mail, fax and telex in addition to other means of reporting provided for in the Civil Arguments Act).)).

It is noted from the advanced text that the Court is able to complete the judicial reporting process in the light of the advantages of modern means of communication in terms of ease of use, speed and low costs, and thus resolve the cases before it as quickly as required by a fair and successful judiciary.

The second requirement

Bio-range for online reporting

One of the reasons for calling for the legal regulation of electronic reporting under the rules of the law of arguments in force is to count as a written report if it is reported by a fictitious address and the case is postponed and then delayed due to reporting more than once;

This can be achieved by electronic reporting, as this report is characterized by rapid communication as a result of the tremendous development in the field of the Internet, the ease of communication between individuals and at this speed reduces the effort for reporting officers, the cleaning of these means when conducting judicial reporting will have an impact when the case is heard and adjudicated so that it is done in a short time compared to if it is reported in traditional ways, as long as judicial reporting is the basis of the proceedings in the civil suit⁽²¹⁾.

Moreover, the conduct of judicial reporting by online means reduces costs for the State Treasury by reducing whistleblowers in the courts and reducing the storage of reporting papers in the courts, where courts⁽²²⁾, through a number of their employees, will archive and store them electronically on computers, and the ease of reference to them when needed.

It is the nature of electronic reporting that it is also characterized by confidentiality, as the reporting information does not enable the non-concerned or his legal agent to access the content of the report, unlike the traditional reporting, which, because of the nature of its procedures, can access its contents, which may affect the reputation of the person concerned with personal or commercial reporting⁽²³⁾.

Also, by using modern means of communication in judicial reporting, we can avoid many mistakes that may occur through traditional reporting methods, these errors can be avoided, especially since the use of technology has become simple and does not require high skill or much effort, and if there are some problems in the use of these methods by giving simple courses to make reporting specialists more knowledgeable, they can make the necessary reports with ease⁽²⁴⁾. The benefits of electronic reporting can be used if they are reported inside Iraq or outside Iraqi borders.

One of the most important and widely used programs of our time in the world is the most important and widely used software in the world because of its rapid exchange of messages and information, low costs, and ease of use, as well as allowing the exchange of e-mails, images and files between people through the information network quickly and at the lowest cost⁽²⁵⁾.

Also do not miss these features reporting by mobile phone messages, it is an important means invented worldwide so that it can communicate via satellites ground and space connected wirelessly to each other and enable the cell phone to send messages and sounds between and the importance of this device reflected the desire of everyone that it is indispensable to become a computer mobile between people and through which to browse through the Internet, SMS is a simple and flexible solution for conducting judicial reports It is rare to see someone who does not have the cell phone, whose use is simple and does not require a certain skill and the court can make notifications with it, does not need access to the Internet and has the advantage of knowing by subscribing to a particular service to verify the message's access to the sender⁽²⁶⁾.

One of the images that we can provide as an example is how we avoid reporting by an electronic means wasted at the time, which may be achieved in the case of if it is to be communicated outside Iraq, if the person to be notified is An Iraqi or a foreigner working in an Iraqi institution abroad such as the embassy or one of the Iraqi accessories, he or she will be notified by addressing the Ministry of Foreign Affairs with the handbook or registered mail and prepares an amount from the date of delivery unless the court is notified of his or her transfer outside the staff of the Iraqi attaché. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs or enjoying leave⁽²⁷⁾, i.e. they are notified by the new department or in their place of residence.

If it is required to be communicated by an Iraqi or a foreigner who does not work in Iraqi institutions, it will be notified by the terms of the Treaty on Judicial Cooperation if any, otherwise, it will be communicated by reference registered mail⁽²⁸⁾, the existence of online reporting will greatly facilitate the work of those assigned to it if it is to be communicated outside Iraq.

From the foregoing, the rapid pace of development, the increase in disputes between individuals, and the slow pace of litigation have become necessary to find precise and rapid means of resolving disputes, which encourages the use of modern means of communication in the field of judicial reporting, as the advantages underlying electronic reporting remove many obstacles to the conduct of reports, with the effect of speeding up the adjudication of the existing case⁽²⁹⁾.

Second research

The impact of the legislation on the positive electronic reporting to facilitate the work of whistleblowers

The rules of the civil arguments law in force are aimed at communicating the right to the owner in conflict or doubting it if the dispute is brought before the judiciary and then considered and adjudicated without delay or waste in the necessary procedures for the right⁽³⁰⁾.

However, electronic reporting lacks a legal presence under the said law and in addition to this we believe that the iraqi signature and electronic transactions law in force, can prepare the legal framework for the use of electronic means in the directness of electronic transactions, including judicial reports, because of its provisions that enhance confidence in the validity and integrity of electronic transactions⁽³¹⁾, but we have noted that this law has excluded from its scope court proceedings and judicial reports by attendance and judicial orders.⁽³²⁾

Therefore, to look at the extent to which the legislation affects the positive electronic reporting to facilitate the work of whistleblowers, requires us to identify the problems of electronic reporting, and this is what we will look at in the first requirement of this research, and thus highlight what can be found in the framework of electronic reporting.

The first requirement online reporting problems

The issue of researching the problems of electronic reporting may include several unspecified problems, but we will identify the most prominent of these problems in light of our research on studies related to electronic means, and what the reality reflects about them, and this is what we will show in the following sections:

Section one

Legal barriers

We mean legislative obstacles within the framework of the role of electronic means in facilitating the work of judicial whistleblowers, the absence of legal texts or the existence of explicit texts that directly hinder electronic reporting or are represented by the existence of texts reflecting the dual legislative position regarding electronic reporting within the framework of the judicial work itself, and this is what we will explain in the following three points:

First. Lack of legislative regulation: -

The legal texts are supposed to reflect and reflect the need of society with its provisions, and therefore those texts are a means of having a dynamic force in satisfying the needs of society, and we do not lose sight of the fact that judicial reporting of the fundamental procedures and the basis on which the implementation of the principle of confrontation between adversaries is based, through which the parties to the case are informed of the papers and the judicial proceedings taken, and also achieve the proper appearance before the judiciary⁽³³⁾.

However, the absence of legislative regulation of electronic reporting under the Civil Arguments Act is one of the obstacles to simplifying the litigation process and resolving cases quickly without delay, and we do not find that the position of the Jordanian legislator is different from what our Iraqi legislator sought; To regulate electronic reporting procedures without establishing legal controls for such procedures, they ensure the integrity of electronic reporting and the wisdom of regulating it effectively. __

Secondly. Legislative exception: -

Our Iraqi legislators under article (2/3, E) of the electronic signature law in force, excluding the courts' procedures and judicial reports by attendance and judicial orders, regulated the legislative framework to work by this law⁽³⁴⁾, and although the electronic signature law in force can be the effective legal basis for the use of electronic means in the directing of electronic reporting and granting legal authority to such transactions and signing electronic signatures by regulating the provisions of electronic transactions, and strengthening Confidence in their health and safety⁽³⁵⁾.

In our view, the legal presence of the exception mentioned in the content of article 3, paragraph II E, is at the forefront of the obstacles to simplifying the formality of litigation proceedings, which is one of the objectives of the influential Iraqi Law of Arguments⁽³⁶⁾, which in turn reflects the simplified formality of the litigation proceedings and the subsequent streamlining of litigation proceedings and the reduction of a lot of time, effort and low costs, which in turn is reflected in the simplified formality of the litigation proceedings and the subsequent Fair and successful.

Therefore, we support those⁽³⁷⁾ who believe that with the exception mentioned, it is not possible to reconcile the legal argument for electronic transactions without others, as the purpose of the legislation of the law is to give

the legal argument for electronic transactions, in general, to be assured by persons in their transactions, and therefore the legal text is a set of harmonized compositions among them leading to a single meaning that indicates the legislator's purpose in regulating it⁽³⁸⁾

Thirdly. Dual legislative position: -

We believe that our Iraqi legislator in the judicial field has placed himself in a position that we can describe as a dual legislative position;

On the other hand, we find that it implies the conduct of electronic judicial communications; article (21) of the rules of procedure for the conduct of the work of the Federal Court, and the possibility of the court directly reporting judicial through modern means of communication, such as e-mail, fax, and telex, therefore it is desirable to unify the legislative position about judicial reporting by modern means to facilitate the judicial process without delay and ease

Section two

Realistic barriers

These obstacles are achieved as a result of the direct reporting procedures of the judiciary at times, and these obstacles can be achieved if judicial reporting is conducted directly by an electronic means, i.e. with the possibility of following modern means by the competent judicial reporting procedure may achieve some of the obstacles, and this is what we will explain in the following points:

First. Under the civil arguments law in force:

We note that under article (26) of the civil arguments law in force, our Iraqi legislator has unified the rules of judicial reporting, without specifying rules for reporting a certain type of case papers, as the provisions in connection with the notification of the petition and its annexes and the papers exchanged in editorial reports and media, and all the judicial papers required to be communicated are consolidated⁽³⁹⁾.

Under these rules, the normal follow-up of judicial reporting may sometimes result in a waste of litigation, whether in terms of time or expenses, for example, what the Iraqi legislator has authorized in the possibility of reporting by mail, if the mail distributor finds that the person to be notified is absent or has no place of residence or a known residence or moved to another place, the main distributor must prove this by delivering the delivery, cover, and book, and return the letter to the court by these In the case, the reporting is only done if it is published in the local press for once⁽⁴⁰⁾, considering that the addressee of the reporting paper is anonymous and that the reporting of the publication indicates that the judicial reporting procedure will take a long and exhausting time for the opponents, and therefore a delay in resolving the case.

The framework of these rules may also result in reporting as if he were to be notified by a metaphorical officer or transferred to another service when his old department received the notification⁽⁴¹⁾.

.In conclusion, the necessity of conducting judicial notification in the traditional manner only, leads to great effort on the part of the whistleblowers, whose duties include conducting judicial notifications, in addition to the consequent lengthening of the procedures and exhausting the litigants; What increases these obstacles is the presence of one of the following assumptions:

1. The capacity of the local areas and the spacing of places of residence for those concerned.
2. The new numbering of the residential houses (alley of the alley number of the house) does not cover all the residential areas, as some of them are still based on the old numbering, such as the areas located on the streets of Al-Kifah and Sheikh Omar, which makes it difficult for those who report to find the residential addresses of the persons to be informed.
3. Failure to indicate the full and clear addresses in the paper to be notified, and the reason for this may be the failure of the two parties to the case to indicate the full addresses in the summons, as required by Article 46 of the Iraqi Civil Procedure Code in force.
4. Failure to indicate the full addresses of those concerned with contracts, contracts, or any other document, especially those submitted to the notary public or other official authorities for ratification⁽⁴²⁾.

Accordingly, the problem of slowness in achieving justice is the real challenge to the rules of litigation in the pleadings law, which aims to achieve the resolution of cases in the shortest time, least effort and minimum expenses without wasting or violating the guarantees of litigation and respecting the rights of the defense⁽⁴³⁾.

Secondly. Within the framework of electronic means: -

We have found that the traditional judicial reporting procedure sometimes leads to a great effort by the whistleblowers, whose task is to conduct judicial notifications as well as the subsequent lengthening of the proceedings and the fatigue of the litigants, but if judicial reporting is followed by electronic means, the whistleblower will be reduced by the effort exerted⁽⁴⁴⁾.

However, this does not mean that electronic reporting is not flawed, despite the speed, security and confidentiality of electronic reporting, but its defects are the frequent disruption of the system, the difficulty of proving access or lack of access, also that activating the reporting procedure by electronic means needs advanced systems and computers requiring high capacity to accommodate programs and applications, but the

advantages of electronic reporting and its work besides traditional reporting prompt us to imitate the sweet It will simplify and facilitate the litigation process to a fair and successful judiciary.

The second requirement

Meditative solutions in the context of electronic reporting

The establishment of an efficient body that fulfills the task of judicial reporting requires that it have all the human and material capabilities available, and we cannot achieve this goal, i.e., access to a successful, low-cost judiciary that achieves full justice ⁽⁴⁵⁾, by addressing the aforementioned obstacles with corresponding solutions that may contribute to their removal and to facilitate the work of whistleblowers on the one hand, and to ensure the rights of litigants on the other. We will therefore discuss these solutions through the possibility of introducing legislative solutions within the framework of judicial work in the first requirement of this research and by identifying some of the practical hypothetical proposals to remove the obstacles to the reality of electronic means, which will be covered by the second requirement to study it.

Section two

Legislative solutions within the judicial framework

We do not take on our Iraqi legislator not to define electronic reporting, because the development of definitions is not a task of the legislator, but we take it to double his legislative position on solutions, which were organized within the framework of the use of modern means of communication and its argument.

In terms of the exception in the article (3/2-E) of the Electronic Signature Act, we believe that our Iraqi legislator was not successful in regulating the electronic signature law in force by excluding electronic dealings in the field of justice and court proceedings, as the purpose of the legislation of this law is to create reassurance among persons by giving legal authenticity to electronic transactions and this purpose does not achieve the desired benefit by excluding article (3/2-e) of the Electronic Signature Act.

As for the ruling of the article (21) of the rules of procedure for conducting the functioning of the Federal Supreme Court, the contradictory position of our Iraqi legislator regarding the use of electronic means is reflected, under that article, the Supreme Federal Court, as part of the Iraqi judiciary, is permitted to conduct judicial reports in its jurisdiction by e-mail and telex, as well as what is stipulated in the applicable Civil Arguments Act.

Based on the above mentioned about the duplication of the legislative position and the resulting contradictory solutions, and given the positive results resulting from the use of modern means of communication in the conduct of judicial reports in terms of simplifying procedures and the economy of time and expenditures, and thus the speed of adjudication of cases without competing with the judiciary, and then what they hope will be characterized as a fair and complete judiciary, we call on our Iraqi legislator to amend the legislative texts on judicial communications by adding a legislative text Judicial reporting of civil proceedings and all related matters is permitted by modern means of communication to facilitate the work of judicial whistleblowers on the one hand, not to exhaust the litigants and to expedite the hearing and adjudication of cases on the other.

It is as if it states that (the e-mail does not lose its legal effect or its enforceability simply because it came in electronic form. ⁽⁴⁶⁾

The information confirmed in the e-mail does not lose its legal authority as long as it has a legal basis for authenticity for electronic signature, namely, the Iraqi signature and electronic transactions law in force, as well as the other legal basis, which is the rule of the article (21) of the rules of procedure for conducting the functioning of the Federal Supreme Court.

Section two

Practical assumptions to remove the obstacles to the reality of electronic means

The issue of delayed reporting, which may be due to the traditional methods of reporting by judicial whistleblowers, needs radical solutions by creating a competent body that will carry out the task and have all the human and material capabilities available, otherwise, we cannot reach the establishment of a successful, low-cost judiciary that achieves the meaning of public justice ⁽⁴⁷⁾.

The use of modern means, whether by mobile phone or e-mail, to carry out judicial notification of it, which reduces the amount of effort and time required for whistleblowers, achieves the speed required to hear and judge the case without wasting the proceedings, and the consequent waste of time and expenditure, but achieving those ends cannot be achieved by obstacles reflected in the practical reality of the use of technological advances in judicial communications.

These obstacles can be overcome and judicial work can be facilitated and simplified if some of the proposed solutions are implemented, which we will show as follows:

First. Infrastructure creation :

The development of such structures requires a qualified judiciary to oversee the use of modern means of communication and to have computers, software, applications, local connectivity, the Internet ⁽⁴⁸⁾, and other

computer equipment to carry out judicial communications for their intended purpose easily and without complications.

Secondly. Ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of information :

To ensure the privacy of the information, the judicial body responsible for electronic judicial reporting must have a document called the Information Privacy Document; The information on the case can only be obtained by persons identified by that entity and are authorized to access the information system and register and access cases such as judges or parties to the case, court staff, lawyers or experts by providing each of them with the user's name and passcode, thus ensuring that unauthorized persons do not enter the information system and access or modify the case papers⁽⁴⁹⁾, which can be done by encrypting information⁽⁵⁰⁾. To ensure their privacy to maintain the confidentiality and accuracy of the information by adopting programs designed for this purpose, to accept judicial reports.

Thirdly, cooperation between the authorities: We mean that cooperation between the judiciary that handles electronic judicial reporting and other state institutions, to take advantage of the databases available to them, such as the use of the databases available to the Ministry of Higher Education for university professors, and this is achieved through the secure networking between this institution and the judicial body that supervises online judicial reporting.

Conclusion

After we have completed our tagged research study (the role of electronic reporting in facilitating the work of judicial whistleblowers - analytical study), we can complete our most important findings and recommendations:

First. Results: -

1. The importance of using modern means of communication by conducting substantial judicial action to achieve the principle of confrontation between adversaries and thus ensuring the validity of litigation without delay or waste in the litigation proceedings is highlighted, namely judicial reporting, as electronic reporting will contribute to reducing and simplifying the formality of litigation proceedings in order to facilitate the court's communication and its aides, particularly those competent in the judicial reporting of cases before it, and to adjudicate them quickly without delay to bring the judiciary to a level where it is due. What it needs to be is a just and successful judiciary.

2. The lack of a legal presence for electronic reporting under the civil arguments law in force with the legal framework for such use, whether within the framework of the Law on Signature and Electronic Transactions or within the rules of procedure for the work of the Federal Court, has placed the Iraqi legislator in the subject of legislative duplication of solutions required by the development and progress of life at times, and the contradictory position in terms of its aim in simplifying the formality of litigation proceedings to facilitate judicial reporting to the conduct of their work with the least effort and efficiency. Another time.

Secondly. Recommendations: -

To transcend the judiciary and facilitate the work of its aides, especially those who specialize in judicial reporting as far as the subject of our study is concerned, we propose the following recommendations:

1. Amending the provisions relating to judicial reporting in the applicable Civil Arguments Act, by adding a provision authorizing the use of electronic means in judicial reporting to facilitate the work of judicial whistleblowers on the one hand and not to exhaust the litigants and to expedite the hearing and adjudication of cases on the other, as if it stated that ((the e-mail does not lose its legal effect or its applicability simply because it came in electronic form).)

2. Amending the Law on Signature and Electronic Transactions by repealing the exception contained in article 3/2-E;

.3It is necessary to appoint a specialized staff for the work of electronic judicial reporting in each court or justice department, with the receipt of the events of formations in all departments of the state to follow up the completion of the reports based on the principle of the need to achieve cooperation between the state departments to stabilize the rights of the owners without delay and within the scope of the principle of economics procedures to reach the general justice that transcends society to the degree of progress.

References

1. Dr. Abdel Moneim Al-Sharqawi, Brief in Civil and Commercial Arguments, Publishing House of Egyptian Universities, Cairo, 1951, p. 267.
2. Dr. Esmat Abdel Meguid, Origins of Civil Arguments, I1, Publications of Ceyhan University, Erbil, 2013, p. 376, referred to the decision of the Federal Court of Cassation No. 7/Personal Status / 2002 issued on 8 January 2002 referred to by Dred Dawood Salman Al-Janabi, chosen in the federal court of cassation district - Division of Pleadings, C2, Sabah Library, Baghdad, 2010,p.60-p61.

3. Dr. Fares Ali Omar Al-Jarjari, *Judicial Reports and Their Role in Resolving Civil Proceedings*, Knowledge Facility, Alexandria, 2007, p. 29, Dr. Ibrahim Ramadan Allam, *Principle of Equality before the Judiciary and its applications in the Law of Pleadings*, I1, Library of Legal Loyalty, Alexandria, 2016, p. 48.
4. Dr. Adam and Heep Al-Nadawi, *Civil Arguments*, National Library, Baghdad, 1988, p. 172.
5. Dr. Saeed Abdul Karim Mubarak, *Civil Arguments*, Mosul University Press, 1984, p. 111.
6. Dr. SaadounNaji Al-Qastini, *Explaining the Verdicts of The Arguments*, I1, Knowledge Press, Baghdad, p. 192.
7. Dr. Mufleh Al-Qadhi, *Civil Due Process and Judicial Reporting*, Culture Publishing and Distribution House, Amman, Jordan, 2020, p. 252.
8. Dr. Awad al-Zoghbi, *Judicial Reporting by Publication in accordance with Jordan's Due Process Law*, Research published in the *Journal of Shariah Science and Law Studies*, Issue 1, Volume 40, 2013,p44.
9. Dr. Ibrahim Mohammed, *The Case between Jurisprudence and Law*, House of Culture and Publishing, Beirut, 2007, p. 161.
10. Dr. FathiWali, *Center in Civil Justice Law I2*, Cairo University Library and University Book, Cairo, 2009, p. 431.
11. Dr. Fares Ali Omar Al-Jarjari, former source, p. 16.
12. Dr. Younis Mahmoud, *Declaration of Judicial Papers in UAE Law and Comparative Law*, Research published in the *Journal of Police Thought*, Issued by the Police Research Center, Sharjah Police General Command, UAE, p. 2, referred to in the work of the Law Conference for Technology 9/11/2000.
13. Dr. Hazem Al-Sharaa, *Electronic Litigation and Electronic Courts*, Culture Publishing and Distribution House, Amman, Jordan, 2010, p. 74.
14. The reasons for the iraqi civil arguments law in force.
15. Hussein Abdul Hadi al-Bayaa, *Explaining the Iraqi Proof Law No. (107) of 1979*, i1, without mentioning the title of publication, Baghdad, 1986,p. 14.
16. Dr. Hadi Hussein al-Kaabi, *Judge's Discretion authority for the abstract element of reality in the civil suit (comparative study)*, Dar al-Sanhouri, Lebanon Beirut, 2019, p. 16.
17. Dr. Hadi Hussein Al Kaabi, *Public Assets in the Law of Pleadings*, I1, C1, Sadiq Cultural House, Babylon, Iraq, 2021, p. 282-p. 283.
18. Dr. Younis Mahmoud, former source, p. 12.
19. Article (3/2-E) of the Iraqi Signature and Electronic Transactions Act.
20. Hossam Obeid, *The Idea of Electronic Judicial Reporting*, Research published in the *Journal of Basra Studies*, Issue 34, 2019, p. 316.
21. Dr. Fares Omar Ali Al-Jarjari, former source, 182.
22. Fares Omar Ali Al-Jarjari, same source, p. 183.
23. Hossam Obeid, former source, p. 316.
24. Dr. Khaled Ibrahim, *Electronic Litigation*, University Think Tank, Alexandria, 2007, p. 98,p. 102.
25. Hossam Obeid, former source, p. 313.
26. AnsamRassamGhadhban, *Legal Regulation of Judicial Communications by Means of Scientific Progress (Comparative Legal Study)*, Master's Letter to the Faculty of Law, University of The Two Rivers, 2016,p. 32.
27. SadiqHaidar, *Civil Arguments Law (Comparative Study)*, Sanhoury Library, Baghdad, 2011, p. 14.
28. (3/2, e) of the same law referred to.
29. Dr. Ali JumaMoaher, i3, *Comparative Law Library*, Baghdad, 2014, p. 3.
30. (3/2, e) of the same law referred to.
- Article 2 of the Iraqi Electronic Signature Act.
31. Reasons for the Iraqi case law in force.
32. Hossam Obeid, former source, p. 323.
33. Dr. SaberNaji Al-Mashhadani, *Legal Structure of The Penal Procedural Text*, I1, Library of Comparative Law, Iraq, Baghdad, 2021, p. 31.
34. Dr. Adam and Heep Al-Nadawi, former source, p. 182.
- Article (20) of the Iraqi Pleadings Act in force.
- Article (21) of the same law referred to.
35. Dr. Ali JumaMo'ad, former source, p. 45.
36. Dr. Ali JumaMo'ad, same source, p. 32.
37. Hossam Obeid, former source, p. 316.
38. Dr. Adam Wahib Al-Nadawi, former source, p. 180.
39. Benefiting from the text of Article (4) of Law No. (1) of 2006, the Transactions and E-Commerce Act.
40. Dr. Adam and Heep Al-Nadawi, former source, p. 167.
41. Hossam Obeid, former source, p. 331.
42. Dr. SafaaOtani, *Electronic Court (Concept and Application)*, Published Research at Damascus University of Legal and Economic Sciences, Volume 28, Issue 1, 2012, p. 177-p. 187.

43. Encryption is a way in which understandable information is translated into incomprehensible information by applying secret protocols that can be reversed or returned to their original state, by having the future of the data in its original form before encryption, and there are several ways to encrypt information, including such as similar encryption and similar encryption, Dr. Fares Omar Ali Al-Jarjari, former source, p. 205, Dr. Safaotani, former source, p177
44. Dr. Adam and Heep Al-Nadawi, Civil Arguments, National Library, Baghdad, 1988.
45. Dr. Ibrahim Ramadan Allam, The Principle of Equality before the Judiciary and its applications in the Law of Pleadings, I1, Law Library of Loyalty, Alexandria, 2016.
46. Dr. Hazem Al-Sharaa, Electronic Litigation and Electronic Courts, Culture Publishing and Distribution House, Amman, Jordan, 2010.
47. Hussein Abdul Hadi al-Bayaa, Explaining the Iraqi Proof Law No. (107) of 1979, i1, without mentioning the publication address, Baghdad, 1986.
48. Dr. Khaled Ibrahim, Electronic Litigation, University Think Tank, Alexandria, 2007.
49. Dr. SaadounNaji Al-Qastini, Explanation of the Verdicts of The Arguments, I1, Knowledge Press, Baghdad, 1972.
50. D. Saeed Abdul Karim Mubarak, Civil Arguments, Mosul University Press, 1984.
51. Dr. SaberInNaji Al-Mashhadani, Legal Structure of The Penal Procedural Text, I1, Comparative Law Library, Iraq, Baghdad, 2021.
52. Dr. Abdel Moneim Al-Sharqawi, Brief in Civil and Commercial Proceedings, Egyptian Universities Publishing House, Cairo, 1951.
53. Dr. Smat Abdul Majid, Origins of Civil Arguments, I1, Ceyhan University Publications, Erbil, 2013.
54. Dr. Fares Ali Omar Al-Jarjari, Judicial Reports and Their Role in Resolving Civil Proceedings, Knowledge Facility, Alexandria, 2007.
55. Dr. FathiWali, Center in Civil Justice Law I2, Cairo University Library and University Book, Cairo, 2009.
56. Dr. Ibrahim Mohammed, The Case between Jurisprudence and Law, House of Culture and Publishing, Beirut, 2007.
57. Dr. Mufleh Judges, Civil Due Process and Judicial Reporting, Culture Publishing and Distribution House, Amman, Jordan, 2020.
58. Dr. Nabil Ismail Omar, Procedural Waste and The Economics of Procedures, New University House, Alexandria 2008.
59. Dr. Hadi Hussein al-Kaabi, Judge's Discretion authority for the abstract reality element in the civil suit (comparative study), Dar al-Sanhour, Lebanon Beirut, 2019.
60. Dr. Hadi Hussein Al Kaabi, Public Assets in The Law of Pleadings, I1, C1, Sadiq Cultural House, Babylon, Iraq, 2021.
61. AnsamRassamGhadhban, Legal Regulation of Judicial Communications by Means of Scientific Progress (Comparative Legal Study), Master's Letter to the Faculty of Law, University of The Two Rivers, 2016.
- 62.. Hossam Obeid, The Idea of Electronic Judicial Reporting, Research published in the Journal of Basra Studies, Issue 34, 2019.
63. SafaaOtani, Electronic Court (Concept and Application), Published Research at Damascus University of Legal and Economic Sciences, Volume 28, Issue 1, 2012.
64. Dr. Awad al-Zoghbi, Judicial Reporting by Publication in accordance with Jordan's Due Process Law, Published Research in The D.A. of Shariah Science and Law Studies, Issue 1, Volume 40, 2013.
65. Dr. Younis Mahmoud, Declaration of Judicial Papers in UAE Law and Comparative Law, Research published in the Journal of Police Thought issues the Police Research Center, Sharjah Police General Command, UAE, referred to in the work of the Law Conference for Technology 9/11/2017.
66. Dred Dawood Salman Al-Janabi, Chosen in the Federal Court of Cassation District - Case Section, C2, Al Sabah Library, Baghdad, 2010.
67. The Iraqi Civil Arguments Act No. (83) of 1969 amended.
68. The Electronic Signature and Electronic Transactions Act No. (87) of 2012.
69. The rules of procedure for the functioning of the Federal Supreme Court No. (1) of 2005.
70. Jordan: Electronic media use system in civil judicial proceedings No. (95) for 2018.
71. Emirates: Law No. (1) of 2006 Transactions and E-Commerce Act.

Author Information

Marwa Abduljaleel Shunabah
Dijlah University College
